

COMPETITION BETWEEN DIFFERENT TOUGHENING MECHANISMS IN COMPOSITES WITH CARBON NANOTUBE GRAFTED FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

Grafting carbon nanotubes (CNTs) on fibers (“fuzzy fibers”) is a promising route to improve the mechanical properties of fiber reinforced composites (FRCs). We propose a two-scale model to reveal the concurrence of multiple damage mechanisms at different scales in CNT-grafted FRCs, i.e. fiber/matrix interfacial debonding, matrix cracking, CNT/matrix interfacial debonding, nanotube breakage and nanotube detachment from the fiber. The virtual experiments show that the beneficial effects of CNTs grafting depend most significantly on in-situ CNTs’ tensile strength and their interfacial cohesion to the matrix. The paper proposes a mapping of the CNT-grafted FRCs failure modes on the parametric space of these two properties and establishes a window of properties beneficial for the toughness improvement. The maximal toughness enhancement can be obtained when the matrix dominates energy consumption through micro-scale damage and CNT debonding occurs locally at the nano-scale. Requirements for the CNT strength and CNT/matrix interfacial strength, necessary for creation of tough hierarchical FRCs are formulated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Structural hierarchy in naturally occurring composites (e.g. teeth, bones, spider silk threads [1, 2]) has inspired the design of man-made fiber reinforced composites (FRCs) towards both superior strength and toughness. Due to the exceptional properties and nano-scale dimensions of CNTs [3], grafting CNTs on fiber surface (“fuzzy fibers”) has attracted widespread attention in the community and shown promise in that regard [4, 5].

The full utilization of this biomimetic hierarchical design, however, has been limited by complex and variable effects of CNT grafting on the performance of the hierarchical FRCs. The beneficial effects of CNTs grafting on FRCs cannot be always reproduced [6, 7], and quantitative improvements of composite properties varies significantly [8], e.g. in the range of 28% to 175% for fiber/matrix interfacial strength (IFS) in [9]. The diverse effects of CNTs grafting are not surprising as various factors are at play, e.g. the density [10], length and orientation [9] of CNTs, grafting strength onto the fiber surface [11], CNT/matrix interfacial cohesion [12] and in-situ strength of CNTs [6].

It is believed that the diverse effects of CNTs grafting originate from the competition between multiple toughening mechanisms, which are rich in in the hierarchical composites, such as matrix cracking, fiber interfacial debonding, CNT interfacial debonding, CNT breakage, etc. As driven by this competition, CNT-grafted FRCs exhibit variety of failure modes. For example, CNTs grafting was observed to shift damage from fiber/matrix interface to resin-rich region in two of the tested samples in [13], but ineffective in preventing the occurrence of fiber debonding in other samples.

From the viewpoint of material design, it is essential to explore how the multiple toughening mechanisms compete with each other and when they can benefit the mechanical properties of FRCs. However, this is challenging as CNT-grafted FRCs exhibit multiple damage mechanisms at different scales [3, 14], e.g. fiber/matrix interfacial debonding and matrix cracking (micro-scale phenomena) as well as CNT interfacial debonding, breakage and detachment with fiber (nano-scale phenomena). Generally, these damage mechanisms occur concurrently and have complex interactions, which is

difficult to model and there has been still no reliable model up to now. The challenges mainly lie in the great difference in the scales of two types of reinforcements: the characteristic length of CNT is ~ 10 nm and that of fiber is ~ 10 μm [15].

In this work, the authors develop a novel two-scale model to account for the complex interactions between multiple damage mechanisms in CNT-grafted FRCs. The objective of this work is to understand when grafted CNTs are beneficial for improving strength and toughness of FRCs and which mechanisms produce the dominating effect.

2 CONCURRENT TWO-SCALE MODEL

Figure 1 shows the three-dimensional (3D) finite element (FE) model for studying the failure behavior of FRCs with fuzzy fibers under transverse tension. The micro-scale reinforcements are carbon fibers with a diameter of 7 μm , and the volume fraction is 60%. A single CNT is assumed to have ten walls, and its length and diameter are fixed to 0.6 μm and 9 nm, respectively. The weight fraction of CNTs relative to carbon fiber is 0.3%, corresponding to 1310 CNTs in the model and 120 CNTs per μm^2 on the fiber surface. The radially aligned CNTs are wavy, and the deviation between local CNT orientation and the direction normal to the fiber surface is less than 10° as in [16, 17].

The micro-scale damage mechanisms include matrix cracking and fiber/matrix interfacial debonding. The nano-scale damage mechanisms are CNT debonding, breakage and detachment from the fiber. The carbon fiber is assumed to be free of damage. To reveal the concurrence of damage mechanisms at different scales, CNTs and CNT/matrix interface are modelled directly. The two-scale modelling combines embedded and cohesive elements proposed in our previous work [18]. This work is the first attempt so far to account for the concurrent damage mechanisms at both micro- and nano-scales in CNT-grafted FRCs.

Figure 1: 3D concurrent two-scale model: (a) unit-cell model, (b) and (c) zoom-in views.

Carbon fiber is considered as transversely isotropic, and the material parameters are taken from [16, 17] and listed in Table 1. The matrix is epoxy polymer, and its mechanical behaviour is described using a ductile damage model developed in [19]. The material parameters are calibrated by the experimental data in [20]. Damage is initiated in the matrix when the maximum principal stress exceeds the tensile strength. The fiber/matrix interfacial behavior is assumed to follow a bilinear traction-separation law. The initial response is expressed as the linear relationship with a stiffness, K ,

$$\tau_i = K_i \delta_i, \quad i = n, s, t, \quad (1)$$

where τ_i and δ_i represent the interfacial stress and displacement in the three directions, n , s , and t , respectively. The damage initiation is governed by a quadratic-stress criterion, i.e.

$$\left(\frac{\langle \tau_n \rangle}{S_n^0}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_s}{S_s^0}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_t}{S_t^0}\right)^2 = 1, \quad (2)$$

where $\langle \rangle$ is the Macaulay brackets with $\langle x \rangle = \max(0, x)$, and S_n^0 , S_s^0 and S_t^0 represent the respective IFS values. The full failure of fiber/matrix interface (i.e. complete debonding) is controlled by the respective fracture energies corresponding to normal and shear tractions, G_n , G_s and G_t . The fiber/matrix interfacial parameters are taken from the experimental data in [12].

The breakage of CNTs is assumed to occur when the maximum principal stress in CNTs is larger than the tensile strength. In the present FE model, a CNT is modelled as an equivalent solid with the strength (σ_{NT}^E) obtained from that of the outer layer (σ_{NT}^L) of multi-walled CNTs:

$$\sigma_{NT}^E = (4t/D)\sigma_{NT}^L. \quad (3)$$

In this work four values of the strength, i.e. 30, 60, 120 GPa and infinitely large (unbreakable CNT), are chosen to account for the effects of CNT tensile strength.

The behavior of the interface between CNTs and the matrix is also described by a bilinear traction-separation law (Eq. (1) and (2)). Herein the interfacial shear strength is assumed to vary from 2.5 to 120 MPa [21, 22], and the fracture energy from 0.03 to 1.5 J/m², so that the effects of interfacial modification can be considered. In the absence of definitive experimental data we assume that the interfacial behavior in the normal direction to CNTs is the same as that in the shear direction.

All material parameters used in this work are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Constituent materials and their properties. Subscript ‘1’ is for the properties in fiber direction and ‘2’ and ‘3’ for the transverse properties. ‘-’ indicates unavailable parameters.

Constituents	Elastic properties	Strength (MPa)	Fracture energy (J/m ²)
Carbon fiber	$E_1 = 276$ GPa, $E_2 = 10.3$ GPa $G_{23} = 3.8$ GPa, $G_{13} = 27.9$ GPa, $\nu_{13} = 0.26$	-	-
Epoxy matrix	$E_m = 3.76$ GPa, $\nu_m = 0.39$	$\sigma_m = 93$	1.0
Fiber/epoxy interface	$K_n = K_s = K_t = 10^8$ GPa/m	$\tau_n = 50$, $\tau_s = \tau_t = 70$	$G_n = 2$, $G_s = G_t = 6$
CNTs	$E_{NT} = 475$ GPa, $\nu_{NT} = 0.35$	$\sigma_{NT}^L = (30, 60, 120, +\infty) \times 10^3$	-
CNT/epoxy interface	$K_n = K_s = K_t = 10^9$ GPa/m	$\tau_n = \tau_s = \tau_t = 2.5 \sim 120$	$G_n = G_s = G_t = 0.03 \sim 1.5$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

For different levels of CNT strength and CNT/matrix IFS, the failure modes of the hierarchical composites can be categorized into four major groups, which are demonstrated in Fig. 2.

I) Excessive CNT debonding leading to fiber debonding.

This mode occurs when CNT/matrix IFS is low and CNT strength is relatively high. Herein CNT/matrix interfacial damage is easy to activate and propagate until CNTs are fully debonded. This is followed by micro-scale damage at the fiber/matrix interface.

II) Matrix cracking and partial CNT debonding.

This scenario occurs for high magnitudes of the CNT strength and CNT/matrix IFS. In this case CNTs strongly contribute to load transfer from the matrix to fiber, which decreases stress at the fiber/matrix interface and suppresses the interfacial damage. Matrix is the weakest link and dominates the failure of the hierarchical composite.

III) CNT detachment-induced fiber debonding.

At low CNT strength and relatively high CNT/matrix IFS, hierarchical composite fails by CNT detachment from the fiber followed by fiber debonding.

IV) Hybrid case of CNT debonding, CNT detachment and fiber debonding.

This mode dominates when the CNT strength and interfacial strength are both low or moderate. The synergy between CNT debonding and detachment from the fiber results in local fiber debonding at the micro-scale.

Figure 2: (a) Damage maps in FRCs with fuzzy fibers and (b) schematic drawings of four representative failure modes.

Figure 3 shows the effects of CNT tensile strength and CNT/matrix IFS on the transverse tensile strength of hierarchical FRCs. By combining Fig. 3 with Fig. 2, it is found that failure mode II leads to the maximal beneficial effects of grafted CNTs. To achieve this, CNT strength should be higher than 120 GPa and the interfacial strength must exceed 50 MPa. The latter can be realized by state-of-art interfacial modification on CNTs [21]. However, the strength requirement for CNTs is challenging as in-situ strength of CNTs in composites is typically in the range of 30~60 GPa [23].

When the in-situ CNT strength is rather low, e.g. 30 GPa, failure mode IV dominates with limited or without beneficial effects of CNT grafting. In this case, transforming failure mode III into IV by decreasing the CNT/matrix IFS can still lead to improvements of composite strength and toughness.

In summary, increasing the in-situ CNT strength always benefits the mechanical properties of FRCs with grafted CNTs. Increasing CNT/matrix interfacial strength is helpful when CNT strength is high, while an intermediate interface strength is required if CNT quality cannot be guaranteed.

Fig. 3. Effects of the CNT strength and interfacial properties on the composite transverse strength.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes a novel two-scale model to account for the concurrence and competition between multiple toughening mechanisms in CNT-grafted FRCs. This model reveals different effects of the CNT tensile strength and CNT/matrix interfacial properties on the mechanical properties and failure modes of CNT-grafted FRCs. The study helps to understand when beneficial effects of CNTs grafting can be obtained and maximized.

CNT-grafted FRCs exhibit four failure modes depending on the CNT strength and interfacial properties: I) excessive CNT debonding leading to fiber debonding, II) matrix cracking accompanied by partial CNT debonding, III) CNT detachment followed by fiber debonding and IV) concurrence of fiber debonding, CNT debonding and CNT detachment from the fiber.

The beneficial effect of CNTs grafting is maximized at failure mode II. In this case, CNTs grafting transfers damage from fiber/matrix interface to the matrix, and delays the damage initiation in hierarchical FRCs. Very weak CNT/matrix interfacial cohesion and low CNT tensile strength lead to the emergence of modes I and III, respectively. A balance between the two nano-scale parameters induces the occurrence of model IV. At very low in-situ CNT strength, CNTs grafting nearly has no improvement of the mechanical properties of the composite in the presence of failure mode IV. In this case switching failure mode III into IV by appropriately weakening CNT/matrix interfacial cohesion can still sustain the beneficial effects of CNTs grafting.

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